

Great Temple of Hattusa

also known as “Temple 1”

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Entry tags: Temple, Archaeological Site, Religious Group, Anatolian Religions, Asia Minor, Religious Place, Religious Complex

The Great Temple, also known as Temple I, was built by the Hittites around 1600 BCE at their capital city Hattuša, located by the modern day town of Boğazkale in the central Anatolia region of Turkey. It is by far the largest of over 30 temples uncovered within the city. The Great Temple was probably referred to as the “Great House” in Hittite texts. Like all of the temples of Hattuša, it belonged to the Hittite state cult that served to the royal administration and was not open to the public. Without any major structural modifications, the temple was in use for four centuries until the end of the Hittite empire in the early years of the 12th century BCE. It appears to have been already emptied and abandoned prior to the destruction by fire. The temple complex is built on artificial terraces in the area called Lower City and is mainly composed of three structures: (1) the temple proper, (2) surrounding storerooms, and (3) an administrative building in the south area. All together they cover an area of 200 m by 130 m (about 6.5 acres). A building on the east side named “House on the Slope” may also have a functional association with the complex. Today, the only remains are the foundations, the human-high base blocks of the walls, and massive door thresholds. Nothing remains of the upper structures that were built of unfired mud-bricks enforced with wood. The temple was probably a single-story structure estimated to be about 5-meters-high, while the storerooms built on lower terraces for the most part had two-, and at the northern end probably three-stories. The temple had 49 rooms of various sizes that surround a courtyard which was entered through a gateway at the southwest end. The largest two rooms, the double adyta, at the northeast end of the temple were accessed from the courtyard by passing through a pillared portico and a couple of small auxiliary rooms, and are believed to have served as the cult rooms for the two top deities of the Hittite pantheon, the Storm God of Hatti and the Sun Goddess of Arinna. Built of dark green gabbro blocks, these two rooms are distinguished from the white limestone of the rest of the temple. While the west adyton is largely destroyed, remains of a stone base that can be seen in the eastern adyton must have been where the cult statue of the deity was placed. Furthermore, five or six other rooms of the temple were likely to have been cult rooms of other major deities of the pantheon. All cult rooms were innermost sanctuaries that could be accessed only by a select few that included the royal family and the priests. In contrast to the Mesopotamian or Egyptian temples, there were several windows that illuminated the cult rooms and the cult statues, although this was probably controlled with wooden shutters on them. The storerooms surrounding the temple numbered at least 200 with the upper stories and were mostly served as depots for various types of goods. Several large pithoi were found in situ, some with a capacity of 2000 liters. Thousands of inscribed clay tablets, mostly fragmented, were recovered from eastern storerooms. The annex building to the south must have been the administrative center of the temple. A text that has been associated with this structure refers to it as the “house of work” and lists over 200 personnel.

Date Range: 1600 BCE - 1180 BCE

Region: Boğazkale, Çorum

Region tags: Middle East, Asia Minor, Turkey, Anatolia

Located within the city walls of Hittite capital Hattuša in central Anatolia, near the Boğazkale town of Çorum province in Turkey. It is about 150 km north of

modern day Turkish capital Ankara.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Schachner, Andreas. "The Great Temple at Hattuşa: Some Preliminary Interpretations." In *Cult, Temple, Sacred Spaces Cult Practices and Cult Spaces in Hittite Anatolia and Neighbouring Cultures*, 105–58. *Studien Zu Den Boğazköy-Texten* 66. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2020.
- Source 2: Neve, Peter. "The Great Temple in Boğazköy-Hattuşa." In *Across the Anatolian Plateau: Readings in the Archaeology of Ancient Turkey*, 77–97. Atlanta: American Schools of Oriental Research, 2002.
- Source 3: Neve, Peter. "Der Große Tempel (Tempel 1) in Boğazköy-Hattuşa." *NüBIA* 12: 41–62.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.hittitemonuments.com/bogazkoy/>
- Source 1 Description: Photographs from the Great Temple of Hattusa and its surroundings.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: As part of the archaeological mission by Ernest Chantre to central Anatolia, trenches were opened in the Great Temple area of the ruins by Boğazköy (the old name of Boğazkale).

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Reference: Chantre, Ernest. *Recherches Archéologiques Dans L'asie Occidentale : Mission En Cappadoce, 1893-1894*. Paris: E. Leroux, 1898.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1893-1894

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Mission en Cappadoce, 1893-1894

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1931-39, 1952-present

Notes: Excavation of the Great Temple was conducted in various years until present time. Major works were carried out in 1937 by Kurt Bittel and Rudolf Naumann and in 1967 by Peter Neve.

Reference: Bittel, Kurt, Hans G. Güterbock, Harald Hauptmann, Hartmut Kühne, Peter Neve, and Wulf Schirmer. *Boğazköy IV. Funde Aus Den Grabungen 1967 Und 1968*. Berlin: Gebr. Mann, 1969.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Boğazköy Excavations by German Archaeological Institute

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Reference: Puchstein, Otto, Heinrich Kohl, and Daniel Krencker. *Boghasköi: Die Bauwerke*. Leipzig: J.C. Hinrichs, 1912.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1906-7 and 1911-12

Notes: During these excavations, a comprehensive survey of the Great Temple area was done in 1907 by the architect, Daniel Krencker, and the archaeologist, Ludwig Curtius in 1907.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Boğazköy excavations by Hugo Winckler and Theodor Macridi.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: There is a natural spring in a small cave ("Quellgrotte") to the south of the temple complex. The spring was a cultic place but it does not play a central role in the Great Temple complex.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although some researchers use the term temenos to define some borders, it is not entirely certain. In a broader scale, the temple complex appears to have been surrounded by the so-called "postern wall" in the south, the "sectional wall" in the west and the northwest, and another structure in the north called "temenos wall". However, at least in certain periods of the city's history there were urban areas that were located to the west of the temple complex, inside the sectional wall. Also, there does not appear to be a boundary on the east side.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: It is located in the center of the Lower City district (sometimes referred to as Old City) of the Hittite capital Hattusa. Although it is in the lower section of the city, the temple was elevated on terraces and was visible from all of the surrounding areas.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Not only it was located within the city, at least for certain periods of the city's history, there were residential quarters right next to the temple complex.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The temple itself and most of the surrounding storerooms and facilities are apparently built in a single stage. Some of the storerooms may have been extended in later periods. From what remains visible today, there does not appear to be an indication that the monumental structures went through any structural change (See Schachner 2020: 147-48).

Reference: Schachner, Andreas. "The Great Temple at Hattuša: Some Preliminary Interpretations". In *Cult, Temple, Sacred Spaces Cult Practices and Cult Spaces in Hittite Anatolia and Neighbouring Cultures*, 105-58. *Studien Zu Den Boğazköy-texten* 66. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2020.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

Notes: Today, only the foundation and the wall bases of the structure, which is made of massive blocks, remain. From what can be observed, researches indicate that the monumental buildings did not go through any structural changes and that the floor

plan remained the same.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: Investigations revealed that the destruction of the temple and most of the surrounding building came with a fire. However, it is noted that the buildings were already emptied and abandoned at the time of fires.

Reference: Seeher, Jürgen. "Die Zerstörung Der Stadt Hattuša". In Internationalen Kongresses Für Hethitologie, Würzburg, 4.-8. October 1999., 623-34. Studien Zu Den Boğazköy-texten 45. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2001.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Notes: There are signs of earthquake damage but those likely to have occurred long after the place was already abandoned.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to multiple deities (see next item).

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The temple has two main adyta, and although there is not definitive proof, it is believed that they are dedicated to the highest deities of the Hittite pantheon, namely the Storm God of Hatti and the Sun Goddess of Arinna (see Neve 2002: 77). Latest investigations further suggest that the other rooms of the temple may have also served as cult rooms for further 5 or 6 lesser deities (Schachner 2020)

Reference: Schachner, Andreas. "The Great Temple at Ḫattuša: Some Preliminary Interpretations". In *Cult, Temple, Sacred Spaces Cult Practices and Cult Spaces in Hittite Anatolia and Neighbouring Cultures*, 105–58. *Studien Zu Den Boğazköy-texten 66*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2020.

Reference: Neve, Peter. "The Great Temple in Boğazköy-Ḫattuša". In *Across the Anatolian Plateau: Readings in the Archaeology of Ancient Turkey*, 77–97. Atlanta: American Schools of Oriental Research, 2002.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no specific information, but it is quite likely that corvee labor and slaves were utilized for its construction, as well as the Hittite artisans and craftsmen that were in the employment of the state cult.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The temple was certainly commissioned and used by the Hittite state cult, headed by the royal family.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Building of a monumental size temple, dedicated to multiple deities, in the early years of the Hittite state must have had political and ideological reasons beyond the religious ones, as manifesting legitimacy and strengthening the unity of the state cult towards establishing a more heterogeneous and common religious and sociocultural identity (see Schachner 2020: 148-150).

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: The temple was a built primarily as a place of worship, but the surrounding temple facilities also housed thousands of inscribed clay tablets a majority of which were cultic in nature although not necessarily sacred.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The structures are built on artificial terraces of varying levels.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

Notes: The complex is mainly composed of 3 large buildings (the temple, the storerooms, and the south building), all of which were separated from each other with paved streets.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The temple building is surrounded with the storeroom buildings. One had to enter the complex through a gateway between the storerooms to reach the street that surrounded the temple.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Upper walls of the buildings were built of unfired mud-bricks, which were made by mixing loam (earth containing clay) with water and adding straw and sand for durability (Seeher 2011: 127f.).

Reference: Seeher, Jürgen. Gods Carved in Stone: The Hittite Rock Sanctuary of Yazılıkaya. Istanbul: Ege, 2011.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Since only remains of the temple complex is the foundations and wall bases of the buildings, almost nothing is known about the temple decorations. However, from the bases it is clear that the temple building was decorated both outside and in the courtyard and cultic rooms with pilasters.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Certain areas of the courtyard and several cult rooms were decorated with pilasters.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The cult rooms of the temple must have had statues/figures that represented the deities, but there are no remains

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Nothing has been recovered from archaeological layers.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: No definitive evidence is found, but the prevalent view is that the two large adyta at the north end of the temple were dedicated to the top deities of the Hittite pantheon, the Storm God of Hatti and the Sun Goddess of Arinna.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Although deities are often depicted in human forms, cultic emblems that represent them could sometimes be in the shape of an animal (such as a bull for storm god) or an object (e.g. a gold disk for the sun-goddess). Nothing has survived from the Great Temple that gives a clue on their representation.

Reference: Collins, Billie Jean. "A Statue for the Deity: Cult Images in Hittite Anatolia". In *Cult Image and Divine Representation in the Ancient Near East*, 13-42. Boston: American Schools of Oriental Research, 2005.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: the Storm God of Hatti and the Sun Goddess of Arinna.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The king was in a liaison position between the gods and the people, as it is stated in a text: "The land belongs to the Storm God alone. Heaven, earth, and the people belong to the Storm God alone. He has made the king, his administrator and given him the entire Land of Hatti."

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: There is no specific information about the Great Temple itself. The answers here are based on what is known in general about the Hittite cultic practices, which should apply to the deities of the Great Temple too.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Through omens, but that does not necessarily take place in the temple.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

Notes: In Hittite culture, divination through human agency does exist, as there are some references to ecstasies (in texts, lit. "man-of-god"), but whether such activity does take place in the temple is unknown.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: Although no remains were recovered it is almost certain that the cult rooms did have the statues of the deities.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– No

Notes: No traces of any cult statues were found.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: Statues were in the cult rooms that were accessible only to a select few people, such as the royal family and the priests.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Notes: Note that this information is generalized from what we know of Hittite cultic practices. There is no specific information about activities in the Great Temple itself.

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: wine and beer

Notes: Wine and beer are the most common, but oil, honey, milk are also mentioned in rituals.

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Typically breads, meat, fat, fruits, sweets, processed goods like flour, ghee, and cheese

Reference: Beckman, Gary. "Opfer. A.II. Nach Schriftlichen Quellen. Anatolien." *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie* 10 (2005): 106-11.

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Sheep, goats, cattle are the most common.

Notes: Birds are also used as burnt offerings. Other wild animals were not considered desirable for the gods and seldom sacrificed for specific ritualistic purposes.

Reference: Collins, Billie Jean. "Animals in the Religions of Ancient Anatolia". In *A History of the Animal World in the Ancient Near East*, 309-34. *Handbook of Oriental Studies* 64.

Leiden: Brill, 2002.

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Objects made of precious metals were offered to gods (see next item), including statues of gods, as well as body parts (such as eyes, hands, breasts, heads) presumably for the existing cult statue, which would consequently become sacred.

Reference: de Roos, Johan. Hittite Votive Texts. Leiden: NINO, 2007.

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: Objects made of precious materials

Notes: Objects like vessels, statues (of deities, kings, queens, animals, model objects), jewelry, symbols, usually made of gold, silver, lapis lazuli, occasionally are some of the items royal family offered to deities.

Reference: de Roos, Johan. Hittite Votive Texts. Leiden: NINO, 2007.

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: services

Notes: Hittite votive texts also mention pledge of certain services such as reinstating certain old cultic festivals, or celebrating them at a certain location for a certain deity, offering persons/slaves to the service of the deity, or setting temples in order.

Reference: de Roos, Johan. Hittite Votive Texts. Leiden: NINO, 2007.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: From mythological texts it is known that the deities care about sex.

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Through divination, although there is no specific information about the Great Temple itself.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Most commonly sheep, goats, cattle, birds

Reference: Collins, Billie Jean. "Animals in the Religions of Ancient Anatolia". In *A History of the Animal World in the Ancient Near East*, 309–34. *Handbook of Oriental Studies* 64. Leiden: Brill, 2002.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Notes: There are no human sacrifices

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– I don't know

Notes: Food and drink offering can be described as mandatory, since they are required for the "sustenance" of the deities. Perhaps other material offerings can be defined as customary rather than mandatory.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

Notes: What is known about this matter from the Hittite texts is almost entirely about the rituals of royal family, the elites and the state cult, and it is unlikely that the ordinary citizens were able to make offerings in the Great Temple. Even the offerings of daily life objects like garments, vessels, goblets, etc are made of valuable materials such as gold, silver, lapis lazuli, rarely iron.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Royalty or their representatives, priests

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– obligatory for some

Notes: The king or a representing royal family member had to travel to various cities in order to attend various festivals. Yet, the Great Temple having been located within the capital was not a site of pilgrimage for the royal family. On the other hand, it is known that for certain cultic festivals, officials from other cities had to come to the capital and to the Great Temple.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is the 'ritual feasting', that is serving food and drinks to the deities. Apart from that, the Hittite cultic festivals also include eating and drinking by the participants, but how much of this takes place within the Great Temple is uncertain. It is known that some festivals involve eating and drinking in the temple, but in most others the feasting seem to take place elsewhere.

Reference: Barsacchi, Francesco. "Distribution and Consumption of Food in Hittite Festivals". In *Economy of Religions in Anatolia: From the Early Second to the Middle of the First Millennium BCE, 5-19*. Alter Orient Und Altes Testament 467. Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 2019.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

– specify: Monthly, seasonal and several other annual festivals

Notes: A list of festivals celebrated in the Hittite capital Hattusa: "the monthly festival, the yearly festival, the festival of the stag, the autumn festival, the spring festival, the festival of thunder, the ḫiyara-festival, the pūdaḫa-festival, the isuwa-festival, the satlassa-festival, the rhyton festival, the festivals of the holy priests, the festivals of the old men, the festivals of the mother-deity priestesses, the daḫiya-festival, the festivals of the upati-men, the pūla-festival, the ḫaḫratar-festivals, or whatever other festival ..." (Instructions for Priests and Temple Personnel, CTH 264, §4). However, there were several other temples in the capital and not all of the festivals may have been celebrated at the Great Temple.

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Beside the royal family and the temple personnel, numerous other officials, functionaries, military personnel, and for some festivals even visiting officials from other cities are among the participants. However, festivals do not entirely take place at the temple complex. Hittite festivals can last several days and take place in several locations.

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– I don't know

Notes: Probably not. Purification, maintenance, repair of the cult statues and the temple structure are the responsibilities of the temple personnel but this appears to be a routine duty regardless of the festivals.

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Difficult to estimate.

Notes: Numerous people are mentioned in the texts: In addition to the king and queen, there are princes, priests, high officials, palace servants, temple functionaries, cooks, waiters, singers, musicians, dancers, various types of guards, and sometimes visiting officials. But it is unclear

how many of them do participate in the parts of the festival that take place in the temple. A rough guess would be a few dozen.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Notes: Food is consumed by pretty much all participants of the festival, which includes the elites and priests as well as numerous functionaries, but the feasts probably take place mostly outside the temple.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Reference: Beal, Richard. "Hittite Oracles". In *Magic and Divination in the Ancient World*, 57-81. *Ancient Magic and Divination II*. Leiden: Brill, 2002.

Reference: van den Hout, Theo P. J. . "Orakel (oracle). B. Bei Den Hethitern.". *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie* 10 (2003): 118-22.

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Extispicy is a common divination method in the Hittite cult, but whether such events take place in the temple is not known.

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In Hittite culture divination through human agency does exist, as there are some references to ecstasies (in texts, lit. "man-of-god"), but whether such activity does take place in the temple is unknown.

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Oracles through observation of animal-behavior (birds, sheep, snakes) is a common

divination method in the Hittite cult, but whether such events took place in the temple is not known.

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Lot oracles (KIN oracles) involve objects that symbolize different elements relevant to the subject being investigated. However, whether such activity took place in the temples is not known.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Dream incubation

Notes: There are references that indicate dream incubation did take place in the temples (de Roos 2007: 22).

Reference: de Roos, Johan. *Hittite Votive Texts*. Leiden: NINO, 2007.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If one has to guess that answer would be no. There is not a lot of information about Hittite healing practices, but from what is available there is no mention of such practice taking place in a temple. Also, in Hittite world healing can be both medical and magical. And in magical rituals, the place of ritual tends to be outside the urban area.

Reference: Haas, Volkert. "Magie Und Zauberei. B. Bei Den Hethitern.". *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie* 7 (1988): 234-55.

Reference: Beckman, Gary. "Medizin. B. Bei Den Hethitern.". *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie* 7 (1990): 629-31.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: As part of festivals

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: There are daily rituals of feeding the deities.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Not enough information is available. I guess would be several dozens in the temple itself.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: At least twice a day for the daily rituals of feeding the deities. The large-scale rituals would be as often as the festivals, which number in tens a year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The fact that step-by-step manuals of many festivals and rituals were kept in writing indicates that correct conduct was important. There are even oracle texts that indicate deities were queried about their approval/disapproval about certain deviations from the regular festival details (Beal 2002: 22f.).

Reference: Beal, Richard. "Gleanings from Hittite Oracle Questions on Religion, Society, Psychology and Decision Making". In *Silva Anatolica: Anatolian Studies Presented to Maciej Popko on the Occasion of His 65th Birthday*, 11-37. Warsaw: Agade, 2002.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Many festivals have to be celebrated with the participation of the royalty and numerous officials.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Consumption of wine and beer was often part of festivals/rituals.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

Notes: The Great Temple had hundreds of personnel. It is likely that some of those had duties elsewhere in the city too.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

Notes: Both male and females were among the Hittite cultic personnel.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not. Names from different cult centers reflect a variety of ethnic origins.

Reference: Taggar-Cohen, Ada. Hittite Priesthood. Texte Der Hethiter 26. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2006. p.170

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are some indications that priesthood does continue within the same families, but that is true for many professions/trades in Hittite society. Yet, there are no indications of restrictions preventing the others from being inducted into priesthood.

Reference: Taggar-Cohen, Ada. Hittite Priesthood. Texte Der Hethiter 26. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2006. p.436

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably not. Priests were appointed by the state administration and could be transferred to different locations.

Reference: Taggar-Cohen, Ada. Hittite Priesthood. Texte Der Hethiter 26. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2006. p.442

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: To a certain degree this might be true as only the temple personnel did have access to "cross the threshold", but it is unclear whether the hierarchy within the

temple personnel did have further levels of segregation of access.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The temple building itself does not seem to have living quarters. Recent studies suggest that all rooms were related to cult activities. However, some of the annex buildings of the complex and the residential quarters to the west of the temple likely to have housed the temple personnel.

Reference: Schachner, Andreas. "The Great Temple at Hattuša: Some Preliminary Interpretations". In *Cult, Temple, Sacred Spaces Cult Practices and Cult Spaces in Hittite Anatolia and Neighbouring Cultures*, 105–58. Studien Zu Den Boğazköy-texten 66. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2020.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Reference: Taggar-Cohen, Ada. *Hittite Priesthood. Texte Der Hethiter 26*. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2006. p.436

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Great Temple was part of the state-run cultic administration. Based on what is known about cultic institutions and Hittite administration in general, temple personnel were responsible for the daily upkeep and cleaning, but administrative officials of the district, and in the case of the Great Temple, the high officials of the city of Hattusa, were responsible for the large scale repairs and even staffing of the temple.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The temples did have extensive inventory lists and detailed record keeping practices, and even audits by the state officials.

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Notes: Temples of the state cult did have property, slaves and goods, and fulfilled a role in the state economy with collection and redistribution of goods, but they did not have an independent economy. They could have been exempted from regular taxes and received wealth from royal donations, but ultimately they all belonged to the king. The Great Temple in the capital city must have been very much dependent on the palace.

Reference: Taggar-Cohen, Ada. Hittite Priesthood. Texte Der Hethiter 26. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2006. p.128–29, 205–8, 442–43

Reference: Collins, Billie Jean. The Hittites and Their World. Atlanta: SBL Press, 2007. p.114

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Notes: The Great Temple was in the service of the royal family. There is no indication that it served to the public.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Thousands of tablets of different genres were found in the annex buildings of the Great Temple. The personnel of the temple included tens of scribes who wrote and copied not only cultic texts, but also administrative, literary and various other types of documents.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has been suggested that the "great house" mentioned in several texts that describe activities in certain festivals/rituals is a reference to the Great Temple. Several texts that mention activities in the

temple of the Storm God of Hatti or Sun Goddess of Arinna in the city of Hattusa may be suspected to be associated with the Great Temple.

Reference: Güterbock, Hans Gustav. "Some Aspects of Hittite Festivals". In *Actes De La Xviiie. Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale*, 175-80. Brussels: Comité belge de recherches en Mésopotamie, 1970. p.180

Reference: Popko, Maciej. "Zur Topographie Von Hattuša: Tempel Auf Büyükkale". In *Hittite Studies in Honor of Harry A. Hoffner Jr. On the Occasion of His 65th Birthday*, 315-23. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 2003. p.315

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Reference: Scientific, Chantre, Ernest. *Recherches Archéologiques Dans L'asie Occidentale : Mission En Cappadoce, 1893-1894*. Paris: E. Leroux, 1898.

Reference: Scientific, Puchstein, Otto, Heinrich Kohl, and Daniel Krencker. *Boghasköi: Die Bauwerke*. Leipzig: J.C. Hinrichs, 1912.

Reference: Year range: 1931-39, 1952-present, Bittel, Kurt, Hans G. Güterbock, Harald Hauptmann, Hartmut Kühne, Peter Neve, and Wulf Schirmer. *Boğazköy IV. Funde Aus Den Grabungen 1967 Und 1968*. Berlin: Gebr. Mann, 1969.

Reference: Burned, Seeher, Jürgen. "Die Zerstörung Der Stadt Hattuša". In *Internationalen Kongresses Für Hethitologie, Würzburg, 4.-8. October 1999*, 623-34. *Studien Zu Den Boğazköy-texten 45*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2001.

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Reference: Yes [specify]: The temple has two main adyta, and although there is not definitive proof, it is believed that they are dedicated to the highest deities of the Hittite pantheon, namely the Storm God of Hatti and the Sun Goddess of Arinna (see Neve 2002: 77). Latest investigations further suggest that the other rooms of the temple may have also served as cult rooms for further 5 or 6 lesser deities (Schachner 2020), Neve, Peter. "The Great Temple in Boğazköy-ḫattuša". In *Across the Anatolian Plateau: Readings in the Archaeology of Ancient Turkey*, 77-97. Atlanta: American Schools of Oriental Research, 2002.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Upper walls of the buildings were built of unfired mud-bricks, which were made by mixing loam (earth containing clay) with water and adding straw and sand for durability (Seeher 2011: 127f.), Seeher, Jürgen. *Gods Carved in Stone: The Hittite Rock Sanctuary of Yazılıkaya*. Istanbul: Ege, 2011.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Most commonly sheep, goats, cattle, birds, Collins, Billie Jean. "Animals in the Religions of Ancient Anatolia". In *A History of the Animal World in the Ancient Near East*, 309-34. *Handbook of Oriental Studies 64*. Leiden: Brill, 2002. , ,

Reference: Yes [specify]: Typically breads, meat, fat, fruits, sweets, processed goods like flour, ghee, and cheese, Beckman, Gary. "Opfer. A.II. Nach Schriftlichen Quellen. Anatolien.". *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie 10 (2005)*: 106-11.

Reference: Yes [specify]: Objects made of precious materials, de Roos, Johan. Hittite Votive Texts. Leiden: NINO, 2007. , , ,

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Reference: No, Collins, Billie Jean. *The Hittites and Their World*. Atlanta: SBL Press, 2007. p.114

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